

NITRATION OF SOME COUMARIN DERIVATIVES

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7-Hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethylcoumarin, its methyl ether and 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin have been nitrated and their nitro derivatives obtained.

Nitration of 7-hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethylcoumarin gave 8-nitro derivative (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 622). It is now found that this coumarin gives a dinitro derivative, 7-hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-6 : 8-dinitrocoumarin, if nitration is allowed to proceed at higher temperature for a short time, and 2 : 4-dihydroxy-3 : 5-dinitroacetophenone, if the nitration is allowed to proceed for a long time. Its methyl ether and acetyl derivative have been prepared. The nitration of its methyl ether either in sulphuric acid or acetic acid gives the same mononitro derivative. As the melting point of this nitro compound is different from that of 7-methoxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-8-nitrocoumarin, it is given the constitution as 7-methoxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-6-nitrocoumarin. The nitration of 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin at room temperature and for a short time gives 3-nitro- and 6-nitro-coumarins. Their methyl ether and phenylhydrazone derivatives have also been prepared.

Prolonged nitration or nitration at higher temperature gives 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 6 : 8-trinitrocoumarin.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-6 : 8-dinitrocoumarin.—7-Hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethylcoumarin (5 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) and nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 5 c.c.) was gradually added to it and the reaction mixture was then warmed on a boiling water-bath until the solid went into solution. Yellow needles, separated on cooling, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 210-11°. More solid was obtained on diluting the original mother-liquor. Alcoholic ferric chloride gave blood-red coloration with the substance. (Found : N, 10.21. $C_{11}H_8O_7N_2$ requires N, 10.0 per cent).

7-Methoxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-6 : 8-dinitrocoumarin.—Sodium salt of the above dinitrocoumarin was prepared by adding 25% solution of sodium hydroxide to its suspension in absolute alcohol and the precipitated salt washed with absolute alcohol and dried at 140°.

The dried sodium salt (1 g.) was suspended in toluene (30 c.c.), dried over Na, and dimethyl sulphate (1.5 c.c.) added to it and the mixture heated at 120° for about 6 hours. The mixture was then mixed with water and subjected to steam distillation. The residue was washed with alkali and finally crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 141°. It gave no characteristic coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : N, 9.6. $C_{12}H_{10}O_7N_2$ requires N, 9.5 per cent).

7-Acetoxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-6 : 8-dinitrocoumarin.—The above dinitrocoumarin was acetylated by boiling for 3 hours with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine. It crystallised from benzene in short yellow needles, m.p. 200-201°. (Found : N, 8.9. $C_{13}H_{10}O_8N_2$ requires N, 8.7 per cent).

2 : 4-Dihydroxy-3 : 5-dinitroacetophenone.—7-Hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-6 : 8-dinitrocoumarin (1 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (15 c.c.), nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 4 c.c.) added and the mixture heated on a boiling water-bath for 1 hour. Yellow cubes separated on cooling the mixture in a refrigerator, m.p. 169°. (Found : N, 11.7. $C_9H_6O_7N_2$ requires N, 11.6 per cent).

The same substance was also obtained from 7-hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethylcoumarin by nitrating it in acetic acid solution with excess of nitric acid on a boiling water-bath.

7-Methoxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-6-nitrocoumarin.—7-Methoxy-3 : 4-dimethylcoumarin (2g.) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (7 c.c.). To ice cooled solution a mixture of nitric acid (1 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (4 c.c.) was added dropwise with constant stirring. It was kept at that temperature for about half an hour and then poured over crushed ice, and the solid obtained was crystallised

from acetic acid in straw-yellow needles, m.p. 232-33°. (Found : N, 5.9. $C_{12}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 5.6 per cent).

Nitration of the coumarin in acetic acid medium on a boiling water-bath for about an hour and a half gave the same substance.

7-Methoxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-8-nitrocoumarin.—7-Hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-8-nitrocoumarin (1 g.), dissolved in dry acetone (100 c.c.), was mixed with methyl iodide (6 c.c.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3g.) and boiled for 24 hours. The residue left after the removal of the solvent was washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution and finally crystallised from alcohol in straw-yellow needles, m.p. 218-20°. (Found : N, 5.8. $C_{12}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 5.6 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methyl-3-nitrocoumarin.—7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin (5 g.) suspended in acetic acid (35 c.c.) was treated with nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 20 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was left at room temperature. After about an hour crystals began to separate which were filtered after half an hour more. (The mother-liquor was worked up separately). The substance was then washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and the solid finally crystallised from alcohol in silky needles, m.p., 217-18°. It gave red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : N, 5.3. $C_{12}H_9O_6N$ requires N, 5.3 per cent).

Its phenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange-yellow needles, m.p. 271-72° (decomp.). (Found : N, 12.1. $C_{18}H_{15}O_5N_3$ requires N, 11.9 per cent).

2 : 4-Dihydroxy-3-acetylacetophenone.—7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methyl-3-nitrocoumarin (1 g.) was dissolved in liquor ammonia (40 c.c.) and the solution heated on a boiling water-bath for about 2 hours. It was then acidified and subjected to steam distillation when 2 : 4-dihydroxy-3-acetylacetophenone was obtained as white needles in the distillate, m.p. 87°. It showed no lowering in melting point when mixed with a genuine specimen.

7-Methoxy-8-acetyl-4-methyl-3-nitrocoumarin.—This was obtained by methylating the hydroxy compound with methyl iodide in dry acetone medium in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. It crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 208-209°. (Found : N, 5.3. $C_{13}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 5.1 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methyl-6-nitrocoumarin.—The mother-liquor from the 3-nitro isomer was diluted with water, when a solid separated. It was warmed with ammonium hydroxide solution and the orange-red filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the solid obtained crystallised from acetic acid in yellow clusters of needles, m.p. 203-204°. It gave red coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : N, 5.4. $C_{12}H_9O_6N$ requires N, 5.3 per cent).

Its phenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in clusters of orange needles, m.p. 230-31° (decomp.). (Found : N, 12.0. $C_{18}H_{15}O_5N_3$ requires N, 11.9 per cent).

7-Methoxy-8-acetyl-4-methyl-6-nitrocoumarin.—It was obtained by methylating the hydroxy compound by methyl iodide in acetone solution in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 125°. (Found : N, 5.3. $C_{13}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 5.1 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-3 : 6 : 8-trinitrocoumarin.—7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.), suspended in acetic acid (8 c.c.), was treated with nitric acid (*d* 1.42, 4 c.c.). After about an hour yellow needles began to separate. The mixture was left overnight at room temperature and yellow cubes were filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 225-26° (decomp.). (Found : N, 13.7. $C_{10}H_5O_9N_3$ requires N, 13.5 per cent).

The same substance was obtained by heating the reaction mixture on a boiling water-bath for half an hour.